

*Cornish language funding 2010-2016 as a political 'bribe'*

Dave Sayers, 20 March 2017

<https://academia.edu/31944206>

During the [Conservative-Liberal Democrat coalition government of 2010-2015](#), [Sir Eric Pickles MP](#) was Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government. In this role, Pickles signed off the first large-scale central government funding for the Cornish language, which varied annually from [£150,000 to £100,000](#) for the financial years 2010-11 to 2015-16. That funding had a real effect on Cornish, enabling for example distribution of learning materials to all schools in Cornwall, and full-time staff to oversee different aspects of the language revival. Although this had only a modest impact on the number of fluent Cornish speakers, it has nevertheless significantly raised the profile of the language, transforming it into a more mainstream symbolic element of Cornish life.

In 2016, following the election of a solely Conservative government in 2015, the funding suddenly ended. The reason given was that such responsibilities were increasingly being devolved to local authorities under the Localism Act 2011 (introduced by Pickles in 2010), which gave local authorities responsibility – though not necessarily money – for a wide range of state activities. A copy of the letter from the Department for Communities and Local Government explaining the decision is archived [here](#). In the context of austerity and significant [cuts to Cornwall Council's budget](#), this effectively ended funding for Cornish.

Pickles left the Cabinet in 2015, received a knighthood, and was appointed the UK's [Special Envoy for Post-Holocaust Issues and Anti-Corruption Champion](#). Freed of Cabinet restraint, he has since had more latitude to speak his mind. On 20 March 2017, he appeared on the BBC's 'Daily Politics' programme, which featured a February 2017 [Council of Europe report](#) urging the government to reconsider "the decision to cut all funding for the Cornish language in view of the disproportionate impact such a measure will have on the delicate process of revitalising a minority language when access to other public financial resources is limited" (p.2).

Speaking with Daily Politics host Jo Coburn, Pickles candidly revealed his motivations for allocating the funding in the first place – a political 'bribe' to secure other budgetary savings from his coalition partners. [A clip of the relevant part of the programme is here](#), with the Pickles interview section transcribed as follows:

JC: So, what say you, Eric Pickles, have you been neglecting your duties and your obligations to the minority in Cornwall?

EP: I am the guilty man. I gave money to the Cornish language when I was Secretary of State. Now before you think this is some kind of revival, I gave it in order that the Liberal Democrats wouldn't block, I think, half a billion pounds' worth of savings.

JC: So it was a bribe?

EP: Oh yeah, absolutely.

JC: Well I can't fault you for your honesty!

EP: I wasn't entirely convinced, but I figured, I think it was thirty thousand pounds (sic) was worth half a million.

JC: Right.

EP: Half a billion.

JC: But you admit that the government's done nothing in terms of trying to actually help or promote Cornish.

EP: I think the government's help... should be to Cornwall, it should be to the people of Cornwall, it should be about industry in Cornwall, it should be about education in Cornwall. I'm not entirely sure. I like the idea that Cornish is going to continue in some form or another, but after all most of that [funding] went in for people learning the language which I'm sure is very beautiful.

Taken together with the letter that explained the funding cut (linked above), this suggests there would have been no central government funding at all without the coalition government. It further suggests that the current Conservative government will not be revising its position on the matter – not least because to do so would be to invite appeals about all manner of other services impacted by the Localism Act.

Some further reading on the recent history of the Cornish revival: <https://www.academia.edu/13099456/>, <https://www.academia.edu/1424269/>.